

RI-VIS - First outreach and partnering event

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Executive Summary

International cooperation in science and technology is an important part of addressing major global issues like climate change, infectious disease, food security, and natural disasters. Research infrastructures (RIs) are organizations that enable scientists to use specific facilities, resources, and expertise to enable and accelerate scientific achievements, overcome boundaries, train highly skilled specialists, and promote sustainable research. Fostering RI partnerships across borders has the potential to improve the efficiency and quality of research to tackle the many challenges faced by society today.

RI-VIS organises the symposia in three different world regions (Africa, Latin America, Australia) to bring together delegates from Research Infrastructures (RIs), science policy organisations and research institutions to discuss opportunities and challenges for RI cooperation between Europe and the respective target region. The aim of these symposia is to raise awareness of individual RIs, to identify measures to mitigate current challenges of international cooperation between RIs, to initiate new and strengthening existing collaborations, and to initiate networks in a sustainable way so that all stakeholders benefit.

The first of these three international symposia was the ‘Africa-Europe Symposium on Research Infrastructures – Exploring collaborations between Africa and Europe’, which was held as a digital meeting on February 1-2, 2021.

Detailed report on the deliverable

Background/Introduction

International cooperation in science and technology is an important part of addressing major global issues like climate change, infectious disease, food security, and natural disasters. Research infrastructures (RIs) are organizations that enable scientists to use specific facilities, resources, and expertise to enable and accelerate scientific achievements, overcome boundaries, train highly skilled specialists, and promote sustainable research. Fostering RI partnerships across borders has the potential to improve the efficiency and quality of research to tackle the many challenges faced by society today.

The aim of WP3 is to increase the international visibility of European RIs, by organising outreach and partnering events with international science policy stakeholders, funders and RIs complementary to the European RI to enable new partnerships. RI-VIS organises the symposia in three different world regions, namely Africa, Latin America, and Australia, to discuss opportunities and challenges for RI cooperation between RIs in Europe and the respective target region. The aim of these symposia is to raise awareness of individual RIs, to identify measures to mitigate current challenges of international cooperation between RIs, to initiate new and strengthening existing collaborations, and to initiate networks in a sustainable way so that all stakeholders benefit.

Description of work

The first of these three international symposia was the ‘Africa-Europe Symposium on Research Infrastructures – Exploring collaborations between Africa and Europe’. The aim is to raise awareness of the different research infrastructures initiatives in Africa and Europe and to discuss opportunities to initiate new (or strengthen existing) bi-regional cooperation.

This symposium was originally organised as an in-person meeting in the Wolfson Pavilion on the Health Sciences Campus of the University of Cape Town, South Africa, on March 23-24, 2020. Due to the ongoing Covid-19 pandemic and travel restrictions, the organisers decided to organise this symposium as a digital meeting on February 1-2, 2021.

The advantages of organising this Africa-Europe Symposium on Research Infrastructures as a digital event were that we were able to reach out to a larger audience, as speakers and participants from outside of Cape Town or South Africa did not need to travel. As no travel was necessary to join the symposium, the time commitment for speakers, attendees and panellists, especially for those from overseas, was significantly reduced. Also, from an environmental perspective, the carbon footprint is reduced compared to an in-person meeting.

Despite these benefits of digital symposia, discussing new collaborative projects and initiating new partnerships benefits from personal interactions, which are difficult to replicate using online tools. Also, in-person site visits, which provide the visitors an ideal insight into the capabilities and operations of the local sites, cannot be realised optimally through virtual meetings. Therefore, in preparation of this symposium, WP3 met and discussed with companies offering all-in-one online platforms to host the event. The following features were considered: live stream videos, chat rooms, exhibitor booths, resource centre, among others. Ultimately, an event platform (Whova, <https://whova.com/>) that offered a variety of different functionalities was been chosen: Attendees were able to submit questions directly in the chat during the respective sessions or submit question in advance under 'session Q&A'. The attendees were invited to prepare their own 'attendee profile' with their information e.g. name, affiliation, position and a short bio sketch, and these profiles were shared with other attendees. The attendees could also contact other attendees directly and send them in-app messages. If they wished to initiate a larger discussion and engage with a broader audience, the attendees could initiate a discussion in the 'community' area by adding a topic or social group. Furthermore, attendees could propose meet-ups and 'virtual meets' and discuss in smaller groups through videoconferencing. The organisers could be contacted by attendees and receive their questions and suggestions through the event platform. Handouts, flyers, brochures and other documents were shared on the event platform, and presentations and longer documents were uploaded in the 'handout' area.

Another important feature was the 'virtual exhibition' area, where RIs and other initiatives and platforms could showcase their work. Through these virtual booths, the RIs could share videos, handouts, marketing content, photos, and even live showcases so that other attendees could learn more about the exhibiting RIs, how to engage with them and what they offer, throughout the symposium. In addition, RI exhibitors could interact directly with the attendees using the chat function of the symposium platform. Once attendees contact the respective RI or request more info, they are able to automatically receive their information.

In our experience from other online events, attendees often hesitate to approach other attendees by using the in-app messaging functionalities, and that the networking experience needs to be supported by dedicated tools. The networking session was supported by the Wonder-App (www.wonder.me), which allows the attendees to interact with each other more organically. By using this networking app, thematic 'room areas' were set-up, and attendees could freely walk through them and talk to other attendees. By doing so, the attendees could network and interact in an authentic way and engage with each other more intimately via these small fluid conversation groups.

The local co-organiser of this symposium was Professor Trevor Sewell at the University of Cape Town. As speakers, panellists and participants, we invited representatives from European and African research infrastructure initiatives, funding organisations as well as independent scientists who are interested in using these RIs for their own research projects. The invited speakers and panellists covered a breadth of scientific fields from the life-sciences to environmental, physical and social sciences. They represented both, European and African research infrastructures (distributed and single-site RIs) as well as funding and intergovernmental organisations (e.g. South African Department of Science and Innovation (DSI), South African Medical Research Council (SAMRC), South African Human Sciences Research Council (HSRC), Scientific Forum on International Cooperation (SFIC), International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC), World Health Organization (WHO), European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI), and the European Commission). Prof. Sue Harrison, Deputy Vice-Chancellor for Research and Internationalisation at the University of Cape Town, Director for the Centre of Bioprocess Engineering Research (CeBER) and Director of the Future Water Research Institute delivered the welcome speech.

Thanks to the support of the speakers and panellists that were confirmed for the original event in Cape Town, the agenda for the virtual symposium (Appendix 1: Agenda) remained with minimal changes.

WP3 took care of the setup of the platform and to integrate all the elements needed to the optimal operation of the event. Below the landing page of the event:

The registration was opened on the 21st of December 2020. There was a total of 474 registrations and 15 virtual booths.

The Symposium took place on February 1st and 2nd, from 10:00 to 16:00 SAST. With 133 attendees from Africa and Europe, see graphic below:

A geographical balance among the speakers, panellists, and attendees was a clear aim of this Africa-Europe symposium. While the lists of speakers and panellists were indeed geographically balanced, the majority of participants came from Europe (see pie chart above). For future meetings, more effort will be needed to raise awareness among the scientific community in the target region.

The engagement of the attendees was high, below we added some statistics.

Engagement with the symposium via social media was also strong. Twitter analytics from the @RI_VIS_eu Twitter account show that over the two days of the event, @RI_VIS_eu tweets received over 30K impressions each day with an average engagement rate of over 1%.

Alongside the planning of the symposium, WP3 worked closely with WP2 to prepare regionally targeted white papers with recommendations to enable bi-regional cooperation of research infrastructures. This was done through literature review and interviews with key stakeholders from each region featured in the white paper. The first of the three bi-regional white papers [1] was published on the 28th January, the week before the symposium.

The findings of the white paper informed discussions at the symposium, in particular during the panel discussions “Opportunities for African-European collaborations between RIs” and “Future of Africa-Europe Research Infrastructure Collaborations”. The symposium thus provided many opportunities for dissemination of the white paper to its target audiences. After the event, a survey

was distributed among the attendees, and the results are compiled in Appendix 2: Post-event survey results.

From the discussions during the symposium, we conclude that there is a growing interest to build and reinforce the collaboration between Europe and Africa, not only with South Africa, but to expand the scientific community. The obstacles that are present are mainly related to funding and the concentration of efforts and collaboration in small areas of Africa.

The attendees shared their points of view about the symposium, which were positive. To see different experts from various backgrounds and scientific fields together was seen as a step forward in the efforts to strengthen the international collaboration.

Feedback from participants regarding the event platform was also positive. As anticipated for an online conference, the face-to-face networking component could not be completely replicated with online networking. Technical barriers and the complication of arranging one-on-one discussions between conference sessions or during coffee breaks resulted in a lower take-up of the one-on-one meetings amongst participants.

Note: The picture was shared on Twitter with the consent of the attendees featured.

The networking session using the Wonder platform, jointly organised with WP4 proved more successful networking session at the end of each conference day hosted in the online platform [Wonder](#). Feedback regarding these sessions was very positive from those who attended the networking session however there was a significant reduction in participant numbers after the main symposium session when transferring to the networking session where approximately 20 participants

joined the networking sessions each day. In future symposia greater efforts will be taken to promote the networking session and explain the change of platform to participants to promote engagement.

Conclusion/Next steps

In general, this was a successful symposium, the speakers, panellists, attendees and RI-VIS partners were satisfied with the platform and content, the challenge is to follow up what it comes from it.

Some partners shared information about working on securing an agreement with African institutions; strengthen existing collaborations or start new projects. For example, Instruct-ERIC has since signed a memorandum of understanding with the University of Cape Town to collaborate on joint activities in the domain of Structural Biology. Another example is the cooperation between EMPHASIS and CGIAR: The Africa-Europe Symposium strengthened the existing interaction between EMPHASIS and CGIAR particularly IITA/Nigeria. There is an ongoing and very successful cooperation based on research projects between key institutions from EMPHASIS and IITA. A number of topics has been identified and both partners are interested in continuing and extending the cooperation in particular when EMPHASIS is fully operational in 2022/2023, which will enable linking IITA to the pan European plant phenotyping community. Directly after the symposium, EU-OPENSREEN discussed with a chemist in South Africa the possibility to exchange compounds, which may potentially lead to closer research collaborations. A similar model can also be extended more broadly and involve other chemists from South Africa and beyond. The symposium also allowed EMBRC-ERIC to meet with the South African Environmental Observation Network (SAEON) for the first time, a meeting that had originally been organized to take place at the symposium in Cape Town. Discussions between EMBRC and SAEON are now underway to explore a possible collaboration between the two research infrastructures.

To address the geographical imbalance between Europe and the partner region for future symposia, we concluded that for the next event, Latin America-Europe Symposium on Research Infrastructures, we will make use of existing networks such as the EU-LAC ResInfra project, with whom we are collaborating in the organisation of the event, to better disseminate information about the event within Latin America, with the aim to have more homogeneous audience.

References

- [1] S. Fahrner, L. Vincenz-Donnelly, G. Pahlavan, R. Pieruschka, N. Pade and B. Stechmann, "Recommendations towards cooperation between African and European research infrastructures," *Zenodo*, p. <https://zenodo.org/record/4475595>, 2021.

Appendices

Appendix 1: Agenda

Africa-Europe Symposium on Research Infrastructures

#AfricaEURResearchInfra

Virtual partnering event

1 February 2021

- *10:00 Welcome of participants
- 10:10 EU international cooperation through RIs
Fadila Boughanemi - Deputy Head of Unit responsible for International Cooperation with Africa, Asia and Middle East, European Commission Directorate-General for Research and Innovation
- 10:30 Introduction to the RI-VIS project
Susan Daenke - Coordinator of the RI-VIS project, Instruct-ERIC
- 10:50 Research Infrastructure landscapes
- South Africa Research Infrastructure Roadmap - Daniel Adams, Chief Director: Basic Sciences and Infrastructure, Department of Science and Technology, South Africa**
- ESFRI Roadmap - Yannis Ioannidis, Vice-Chair of the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI)**
- Africa-Europe Research and Innovation Cooperation - Mariella Di Ciommo, Policy Officer in the European External Affairs programme at the European Centre for Development (ECDFM)**
- 12:00 Lunch break
- 13:00 Expanding African-European partnerships - New Opportunities and Synergies - Part 1
- Synchrotron Techniques for African Research and Technology (START) - Trevor Sewell, University of Cape Town, South Africa; and National Coordinator of the bioscience component of START**
- The European Research Infrastructure in Chemical Biology and Early Drug Discovery (EU-OPENSCREEN) - Bahne Stechmann, EU-OPENSCREEN ERIC**
- The European Research Infrastructure on Highly Pathogenic Agents (ERINHA) - Hervé Raoul, ERINHA**
- The Square Kilometre Array (SKA) - Carla Sharpe, SKA/VLBI**
- Taita Research Station of the University of Helsinki, Taita Taveta County, Kenya - Petri Pellikka, University of Helsinki, Institute for Atmospheric and Earth System Research (INAR)**
- The South African Social Attitudes Survey (SASAS) - Ben Roberts, Coordinator of South African Social Attitudes Survey (SASAS), HRSC**
- 14:30 Panel discussion: Opportunities for African-European collaborations between Research Infrastructures
- Daniel Adams, Chief Director: Basic Sciences and Infrastructure, Department of Science and Technology, South Africa*
Yannis Ioannidis, Vice-Chair of the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI)
Trevor Sewell, University of Cape Town
Mariella Di Ciommo, Policy Officer in the European External Affairs programme at the European Centre for Development (ECDFM)
- 15:45 Conclusions from Day 1
- 16:00 Networking session on "Wonder"

*Times are given in SAST = GMT + 2 = CET + 1

2 February 2021

- *10:00 African-European collaborations within global Research Infrastructures
- African European Radio Astronomy Platform (AERAP) - Declan Kirrane, Coordinator of AERAP**
- The Bridging Biobanking and Biomedical Research Across Europe and Africa (B3Africa) project and the European research infrastructure for biobanking (BBMRI) - Akin Abayomi, University of Stellenbosch**
- The Clinical Research Initiative for Global Health (CRIGH) and the European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network (ECRIN) - Golbahar Pahlavan, European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network (ECRIN)**
- World Federation of Culture Collections and the Microbial Resource Research Infrastructure (MIRRI) - Philippe Desmeth, BELSPO**
- Global-Bioluminescence and South Africa Bioluminescence - Ben Loos, Stellenbosch University, South Africa**
- The SEACRIFOG (Supporting EU-African Cooperation on Research Infrastructures for Food Security and Greenhouse Gas Observations) project: EU-African Cooperation on RIs for Food Security and Greenhouse Gas Observations - Mylène Ndisi, Université Clermont Auvergne, France**
- 11:30 Expanding African-European partnerships - New Opportunities and Synergies - Part 2
- The perspective of an intergovernmental agency on how to collaborate with Research Infrastructures - Zisis Kozlakidis, International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC)/ World Health Organization (WHO)**
- CGIAR: Global Partnerships in agricultural research and food-security - Michael T. Abberton - International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA), CGIAR, Ibadan, Nigeria**
- Strategic African Initiatives: The African Laser Centre (ALC) and the African Light Source (AFLS) - Sekazi Mtingwa, Co-Founder of the African Laser Centre and the African Light Source Foundation, and TriSEED Consultants, USA**
- INFRAFRONTIER and the International Mouse Phenotyping Consortium (IMPC) - Asrar Ali Khan, INFRAFRONTIER, Munich, Germany**
- 12:30 Lunch break
- 13:30 Panel discussion: Future of Africa-Europe Research Infrastructure Collaborations
- Daniel Adams, Chief Director: Basic Sciences and Infrastructure, Department of Science and Technology, South Africa*
Golbahar Pahlavan, European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network (ECRIN)
Richard Gordon, Executive Director: Grants Innovation and Product Development, South African Medical Research Council (SAMRC)
Johannes Klumpers, Head of the Unit 'Research and Industrial Infrastructures', European Commission Directorate-General for Research and Innovation
- 15:30 Conclusions from the Africa-Europe Symposium and Closing Remarks
- 16:00 Informal networking

<http://bit.ly/ri-vis-africa>

ri-vis.eu

@RI_VIS_eu

RI-VIS

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Appendix 2: Post-event survey results

Timestamp	What are your key take-home messages from this symposium?	Please comment on what you liked about the symposium and your recommendations on what could be improved?	Overall, did the sessions meet your expectations?	Which session did you like in particular?	How valuable were the networking opportunities?	Did the symposium structure give ample time to interact with other attendees?	Are you interested in a follow-up symposium in the future?	Would you recommend the symposium to others?	How well organized was the conference?	How would you rate the Whova app?
02/02/2021 13:59:00	There untapped opportunities for Africans researchers to use RI. The partnerships can foster research in Africa where the facilities have not been established. Still as kind can Africa - EU RI help in building a strong force of expertise in important areas in other African countries like in Kenya?	There's was low level of awareness of this symposium in Africa reflected by the number of attendees from Africa. More from EU stakeholders	Yes	Emphasis	Very	Yes	Yes	Yes	Very	Excellent
02/02/2021 15:32:00	So many things taking place already	Keeping in the timetable	Yes	Tuesday afternoon	Very	No	Yes	Yes	Very	Very good
02/02/2021 15:34:00	There is real opportunity for collaboration but the challenge is mainly financial	There was a good coverage of talks, but a shame that there was not more on environmental research. The African representatives seemed very well prepared and lots of ideas to do things. The European Commission much less so...	Yes	Panel discussions	Very	Yes	Yes	Yes	Very	Very good
02/02/2021 15:36:00	There are many opportunities for partnerships in building large infrastructures, as well as smaller facilities that feed into those infrastructures. The LAAAMP (https://laaamp.iucr.org/) project in which I am involved is active in Mexico, Central America, and the Caribbean. Please keep me up to date on the next RI-VIS in Latin America.	The participants were absolutely top people in their fields. No ideas for improving THE perfect meeting.	Yes	All	Extremely	Yes	Yes	Yes	Extremely	Excellent
02/02/2021 16:07:00	Landscape analysis and strategies of RIs based on: - Concept Development - Design - Preparation - Implementation and Operation - Evaluation	Extend the speakers list by adding or contacting other Africa Countries Programme or Initiative e.g AU-NEPAD Biosciences Expert.	Yes	1. Research Infrastructure landscapes 2. Expanding African-European partnerships- New Opportunities and Synergies-Part 1 & 2 3. Panel discussion: Future of Africa-Europe Research Infrastructure Collaborations	Very	Yes	Yes	Yes	Extremely	Very good
02/02/2021 16:36:00	There are many initiatives and infrastructures in both Africa and Europe, but collaboration between them needs to be strengthened, as well as strengthening the already existing collaborations.	The quality of the presentations and the experience of the speakers.	Yes	The Bridging Biobanking and Biomedical Research Across Europe and Africa (B3Africa) project and the European research infrastructure for biobanking (BBMRI) - Akin Abayomi, University of Stellenbosch	Somewhat	No	Yes	Yes	Very	Very good
02/02/2021 21:16:00	A willingness of the scientific community to expand the collaboration between Africa and Europe. Scientific activities and major programmes are concentrated in some African countries. It is necessary to expand the scientific programmes to a larger geographical area, as far as the political and security situation allows such extension. That requires a political willingness and large investments. RI may contribute to argue and convince the decisionmakers.	The chairs and the organizers were efficient in handling time and properly ran the discussions.	Yes	All sessions as they illustrate different situation; those that are familiar and others that are interesting to learn more about.	Somewhat	Yes	Yes	Yes	Extremely	Very good
03/02/2021 10:19:00	Important topic, needs to be discussed further in the future. Important that RIs and policy makers discuss together - instead of RIs among each other or policy makers among each other. Event encouraged me to reach out to partners and discuss new partnerships	Excellent speakers, interesting talks, plenty of opportunities to network, good organization.	Yes	all	Extremely	Yes	Yes	Yes	Extremely	Excellent
03/02/2021 10:44:00	To develop better collaboration with researchers where it is possible	I think the agenda was very good, speakers were excellent. The access to the event seemed not easy the first day.	Yes	I think all sessions are very interesting. I liked the panel discussion on perspectives of EU-AFRICA collaboration.	Very	Yes	Yes	Yes	Extremely	Excellent
03/02/2021 11:15:00	Funding, Mutual benefit, and data openness and sharing are critical to collaboration between Africa and Europe. Brain-drain is an issue to bear in mind and how infrastructures can prevent it.	Selection of speakers was excellent. Consider more breaks for networking.	Yes	Networking session was better than expected and platform offered a good format for small group discussions. From the main symposium panel discussions and RI presentations were good.	Extremely	No	Yes	Yes	Extremely	Very good
03/02/2021 11:43:00	Partnerships between the EU and Africa remain a priority for science collaboration and human well being. Some issues are new, but others were there 10 years ago as addressed by PAERIP	Well chosen speakers, good moderation and lively interaction of participants On a technical level, the Whova/Zoom interface is not mature yet and the restriction of browsers for access is not ideal.	Yes	The two panel discussions	Somewhat	Yes	Yes	Yes	Very	Fair
03/02/2021 11:57:00	That we need to strengthen the cooperation in the scientific field between Africa and Europe. Africa, despite the scarcity of funding and the fragmentation problems, can offer huge opportunities to help tackle the global challenges that affect all of us.	I liked very much the whole idea of this kind of symposium. It was very nice to put together different experts from various backgrounds and scientific fields. It was very nice also to have the opportunity to ask questions through the chat and to network at the end. The only negative comment: maybe it would have been better to have less talks and more time to ask questions. I really liked Wonder tool for networking!	Yes	the ones on the ESFRI roadmap, on EU OPENSREEN, on ERINHA, on ECRIN, on AFIS, on INFRAFRONTIER	Very	No	Yes	Yes	Very	Very good

<p>03/02/2021 13:47:00</p>	<p>I have learned both about EU projects and opportunities for collaboration with Africa.</p> <p>I have some criticism with the platform, but as they don't fit into the allowed number of characters (which is actually non specified) I and spreading them in all the window.</p>	<p>Too much emphasis on science politics - I would have liked a more practical slant.</p> <p>The interface (at least the web-based interface) was rather unfriendly - a simple Zoom platform would have been easier to use and navigate. When I clicked onto Chat or Participants the window opened in the middle of the speaker screen, and to close it I was forced to exit and re-enter.</p> <p>For example this feedback window has a character limits, but I don't know how many chars are allowed - not very friendly.</p>	<p>Yes</p>	<p>I have Expanding African-European partnerships - New Opportunities and Synergies.</p> <p>I have not understood how to joint the interaction rooms, so I had no opportunities for networking.</p> <p>It may have been easier if one downloaded the phone app, but I don't want to follow a conference on a mobile, when I can use my computer. Nor I want to download an app that I am using only once.</p>	<p>Not so</p>	<p>No</p>	<p>Yes</p>	<p>Yes</p>	<p>Somewhat</p>	<p>Poor</p>
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AFRICA-EUROPE SYMPOSIUM ON RESEARCH INFRA STRUCTURES

AFRICA-EUROPE SYMPOSIUM ON RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES

FEBRUARY 1 - 2, 2021

9:41 Home

Africa-Europe Symposium on Research Infrastructures
Exploring collaborations between Africa and Europe
1-2 February 2021
Virtual partnering event

Africa-Europe Symposium on Research Infrastr...
San Diego, CA
Feb 1 - 2, 2021
View Location

Additional Resources

- Leaderboard
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Event Description
The premier event for innovative

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whoava app USAGE HIGHLIGHTS

OVERALL DOWNLOAD RATE

72% ATTENDEE DOWNLOAD RATE FOR WHOVA EVENTS
71%

SPEAKERS DOWNLOAD RATE

68% SPEAKERS DOWNLOADED
19 of 28

ATTENDEES LOVED OUR APP

89% TOOK THE SURVEY
8

PROFILE VIEWS IN APP

390

ATTENDEE NETWORKING

PHOTOS SHARED: 52
BUSINESS CARD EXCHANGED: 8

ANNOUNCEMENT OPEN RATE

58%

ANNOUNCEMENTS VIA IN-APP NOTIFICATIONS AND EMAILS
4

ANNOUNCEMENTS

- Join the Virtual Networking session
- Panel discussion: Future of Africa-Eur...
- Join the Virtual Networking session
- Africa-Europe Symposium on Resear...

whoava app COMMUNITY BOARD

DISCUSSION TOPICS POSTED

22

COMMUNITY BOARD TOTAL MESSAGES

163

MOST POPULAR DISCUSSION TOPICS

- **Session Q&A**
32 messages
- **Marine Biological Resources**
25 messages
- **Article Sharing**
22 articles shared
- **Exhibitor Showcase**
10 messages
- **Organizer Announcements**
8 messages

whova app AGENDA HIGHLIGHTS

AGENDA IN-APP VIEWS

764

PERSONAL AGENDA SET-UP BY ATTENDEES

54

PERCENTAGE OF ATTENDEES SET
27%

AGENDA SESSIONS MOST POPULAR

SESSION POPULARITY BASED ON LIKES AND PERSONAL AGENDA ADDS

- Panel discussion: Future of Africa-Europe Research Infrastructure Collaborations
14 personal agenda adds
- African-European collaborations within global Research Infrastructures
18 personal agenda adds
- Panel discussion: Opportunities for African-European collaborations between RIs
16 personal agenda adds
- Conclusions from the Africa-Europe symposium and Closing Remarks
11 personal agenda adds
- Welcome of participants
12 personal agenda adds

whova app MARKETING TOOLS YOU USED

AGENDA WEBPAGE VIEWS

2105

Your Agenda
Webpage Design
<https://whova.com/embedded/ev...>

REGISTRATION

258

whova app MOBILE & WEB APP ACTIVE USERS

TOTAL ACTIVE USERS

199

USERS WHO SIGNED IN EITHER MOBILE
OR WEB APP

USED BOTH MOBILE & WEB APP

61

USERS WHO DOWNLOADED THE MOBILE AND
SIGNED IN TO WEB APP

MOBILE APP ACTIVE USERS

48%

ATTENDEES WHO USED THE MOBILE
APP
97/199

WEB APP ACTIVE USERS

75%

ATTENDEES WHO USED THE WEB
APP
150/199

whova app COMMUNITY HIGHLIGHTS

DISCUSSION TOPICS POSTED

22

COMMUNITY BOARD TOTAL MESSAGES

163

BREAK-THE-ICE MESSAGES

18

JOB POSTING MESSAGES

4

ARTICLE SHARED MESSAGES

17

MOST FOLLOWED DISCUSSIONS

- Session Q&A
10 people followed this topic
- Biobanking
8 people followed this topic
- Job Openings
4 people followed this topic

PHOTOS SHARED

52

TOTAL LIKES FOR ALL PHOTOS

1

POPULAR PHOTOS MOST LIKED

whova app ATTENDEE VIEWING ACTIVITY

ATTENDEES WATCHED TOTAL

103 TOTAL DURATION WATCHED
410 HRS

SESSIONS WITH VIDEO OR STREAM

27

WATCHED SESSIONS MOST POPULAR STREAMS

SESSION POPULARITY BASED ON NUMBER OF ATTENDEES

1. Expanding African-European partnerships – New Opportunities and Synergies, Part I
119.7 hours, watched by 61 attendees
2. Panel discussion: Future of Africa-Europe Research Infrastructure Collaborations
79.0 hours, watched by 53 attendees
3. African-European collaborations within global Research Infrastructures
89.0 hours, watched by 46 attendees

whoava app

NETWORKING HIGHLIGHTS

PRIVATE MESSAGES 1-ON-1

310

ATTENDEE INTERACTION 1-ON-1

283

Attendees who have interacted with each other in private 1-on-1 messages

ATTENDEES INDICATED INTEREST

37

RECOMMENDED ATTENDEES

106

ATTENDEES MATCHED BASED OFF OF INTERESTS, LOCATIONS, AFFILIATION

TOP RECOMMENDATION MATCHES

structural biology, biochemistry, cape tow, molecular genetics, personal genomics medicine, genomics, bioinformatics, greater paris metropolitan regio, south afric, and more...

BIZ CARD SCANNED AND EXCHANGED

8

ATTENDEES PROFILE VIEWS

390

whova app ATTENDEE BREAKDOWN

ATTENDEE CATEGORIES

TOP 5 ATTENDEE CATEGORIES

Category	ATTENDEES
All attendees not in other categories	229
Speakers	28
Exhibitors	20
Organizers	4
Panelists	0

ATTENDEE AFFILIATION

TOP 5 ATTENDEE AFFILIATION

Affiliation	ATTENDEES
Instruct-ERIC	5
EMPHASIS	4
University	4
University of Cape Town	3
University of the Free State	3

MOST ACTIVE ATTENDEES

TOP 5 MOST ACTIVE BY APP ACTION

Rank	ACTIONS
1	290
2	163
3	143
4	138
5	120

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AGENDA WEBPAGE URL

<https://ri-vis.eu/>

WHOVA TEMPLATE USED

SIMPLY

Event Agenda

Expanded View ▾

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🔍 Search

📅 Filter by date

- Monday, Feb 1
- Tuesday, Feb 2

🟢 Filter by track

- Sample Track One
- Sample Track Two
- No specified track

📍 Displaying agenda in your event timezone (5:33 PM SAST)

Monday, February 1

10:00 am - 10:10 am	<p>Welcome of participants</p> <p>📺 Live Stream: Join stream</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bahne Stechmann (Speaker) Head of Operations & Scientific Strategy, EU-OPENSREEN Sue Harrison (Speaker) DVC: Research and Internationalisation, UCT 	📺
10:10 am - 10:25 am	<p>EU international cooperation through RIs</p> <p>📺 Live Stream: Join stream</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fadila Boughanemi (Speaker) Commission européenne Bahne Stechmann (Chair) Head of Operations & Scientific Strategy, EU-OPENSREEN <p>International cooperation in research and innovation is a strategic priority for the EU. It enables:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> access to the latest knowledge and the best talent worldwide business opportunities in new and emerging markets science diplomacy to influence an... <p>See More</p>	📺
10:30 am - 10:50 am	<p>Introduction to the RI-VIS Project</p> <p>📺 Live Stream: Join stream</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Susan Daenke (Speaker) Instruct-ERIC Coordinator / European Projects Programme Manager, University of Oxford Bahne Stechmann (Chair) Head of Operations & Scientific Strategy, EU-OPENSREEN <p>RI-VIS is an EU-funded project to increase the knowledge and visibility for European research infrastructures that now form a valuable core of service providers for European researchers across the domains of life sciences, physics and engineering.... See More</p>	📺
10:50 am - 12:00 pm	<p>Research Infrastructure landscapes</p> <p>📺 Live Stream: Join stream</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bahne Stechmann (Chair) Head of Operations & Scientific Strategy, EU-OPENSREEN <p>3 subsessions</p>	📺
12:00 pm - 1:00 pm	<p>Lunch Break</p>	📺
1:00 pm - 2:30 pm	<p>Expanding African-European partnerships - New Opportunities and Synergies, Part I</p> <p>📺 Live Stream: Join stream</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Jens Habermann (Chair) Director General, BBMRI-ERIC <p>6 subsessions</p>	📺
2:30 pm - 3:45 pm	<p>Panel discussion: Opportunities for African-European collaborations between RIs</p> <p>📺 Live Stream: Join stream</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sven Fahrner (Chair) EMPHASIS Daniel Adams (Panelist) Chief-Director: Basic Sciences and Infrastructure, Department of Science and Innovation, South Africa Yannis Ioannidis (Panelist) President and General Director / Professor of Informatics, Athena Research and Innovation Center / University of Athens Trevor Sewell (Panelist) Senior Scholar / Professor of Medical Biochemistry and Director of the Electron Microscope Unit, University of Cape Town Mariella Di Ciommo (Panelist) Policy Officer II, European External Affairs programme at the European Centre for Development (ECDFM) 	📺
3:45 pm - 4:00 pm	<p>Conclusions from Day 1</p> <p>📺 Live Stream: Join stream</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Susan Daenke (Speaker) Instruct-ERIC Coordinator / European Projects Programme Manager, University of Oxford 	📺
4:00 pm - 6:00 pm	<p>Virtual Networking Session on "Wonder"</p> <p>📺 Live Stream: Join stream</p>	📺

Virtual Networking Sessions

▶ Video chats in small circles

AFRICA-EUROPE SYMPOSIUM ON RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES

TOTAL AGENDA WEBPAGE VIEWS

2105

agenda stats shown are not from the app

INDIVIDUAL AGENDA TOTAL VIEWS

2128

agenda stats shown are not from the app

TOP 10 AGENDAS

1. African-European collaborations within global Research Infrastructures
2. Expanding African-European partnerships - New Opportunities and Synergies - Part 2
3. Panel discussion: Future of Africa-Europe Research Infrastructure Collaborations
4. Research Infrastructure landscapes
5. EU international cooperation through RIs
6. Virtual Networking Session on "Wonder"
7. Virtual Networking Session on "Wonder"
8. Introduction to the RI-VIS Project
9. Expanding African-European partnerships – New Opportunities and Synergies, Part I
10. Panel discussion: Opportunities for African-European collaborations between RIs

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Speakers

 Ben Roberts Research Director and Coordinator... Human Sciences Research Council...			
 Fadila Boughanemi Commission européenne			
 Jens Habermann Director General BBMRI-ERIC			
 Mylène S. Ndisi PhD Student - Public Policy... Université Clermont...			
 Prof Akin Abayomi Honourable Commissioner fo... Lagos State Ministry of Health			

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Africa-Europe Symposium on Research Infrastructures

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All Exhibitors

-

African Laser Centre and the African Light Source Foundation and TriSEED Consultants

Both programs are enhancing research and training capacity in science and technology throughout Africa.
-

BBMRI-ERIC

BBMRI-ERIC is a European research infrastructure for biobanking. We bring together all the main players from the biobanking field – researchers, biobankers, industry, and patients – to boost biomedical research. To that end, we offer quality manag...
-

ECRIN-ERIC

ECRIN is a public, non-profit organisation that links scientific partners and networks across Europe to facilitate multinational clinical research. We provide sponsors and investigators with advice, management services and tools to overcome hurdle...
-

EMBRC

EMBRC, the European Marine Biological Resource Centre, is Europe's research infrastructure for marine biological resources and marine ecosystems. We provide access to wild-type macro and microorganisms, culture collections of microorganisms, and a...
-

EMPHASIS

The European research infrastructure EMPHASIS will enable researchers to use facilities, resources and services for plant phenotyping across Europe. Our vision is to help scientists better understand plant performance and translate this knowledge ...
-

ENVRI

European environmental research infrastructures are the key providers of high-quality data, research products and services from key components of the Earth system - Atmosphere, Marine, Solid Earth, and Biodiversity / Terrestrial Ecosystems.

Unde...
-

ERINHA

ERINHA is a pan-European distributed Research Infrastructure dedicated to the study of high-consequence emerging and re-emerging pathogens.

It brings together leading European Bio-Safety Level 4 and complementary (e.g. BSL3) facilities with longs...
-

ESFRI
-

ESS ERIC

The European Social Survey (ESS) is an academically driven cross-national survey that has been conducted across Europe since its establishment in 2001. Every two years, face-to-face interviews are conducted with newly selected, cross-sectional sam...
-

EU-OPENSREEN

EU-OPENSREEN integrates high-capacity screening platforms throughout Europe, which jointly use a rationally selected compound collection, comprising up to 140.000 commercial and proprietary compounds collected from European chemists. EU-OPENSREEN...
-

Global Biolmaging

Global Biolmaging is the international network of imaging infrastructures and communities. We foster collaboration between a wide range of international partners, including South Africa Biolmaging. We provide a unique opportunity for international...

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TICKETS WHOVA SOLD

258

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registration

Africa-Europe Symposium on Research Infrastructures

February 1 - 2, 2021 (SAST)

Ticket

General Admission	Sales end
Sales end: 2021-02-05T00:00:00 (Africa/Johannesburg)	

[Register](#)

Event Description

It is our pleasure to welcome you to the Africa-Europe Symposium on Research Infrastructures.

International cooperation in science and technology is an important part of addressing major global issues like climate change, infectious disease, food security, and natural disasters. Research infrastructures (RIs) are organizations that enable scientists to use specific facilities, resources, and expertise to enable and accelerate scientific achievements, overcome boundaries, train highly skilled specialists, and promote sustainable research. Fostering RI partnerships across borders has the potential to improve the efficiency and quality of research to tackle the many challenges faced by society today.

The virtual two-day symposium brings together delegates from African and European Research Infrastructures (RIs), science policy organisations and research institutions to discuss opportunities and challenges for RI cooperations between Africa and Europe.

We hope to raise awareness of individual RIs, to identify measures to mitigate current challenges of biregional cooperations between RIs, to initiate new and strengthening existing collaborations, and to initiate networks in a sustainable way so that all stakeholders benefit.

We invite all researchers who have an interest in learning more about Research Infrastructures and the research opportunities they offer to scientists. Participation in this event is for free, but [registration](#) is required.

This symposium is organised as part of the RI-VIS project, a Horizon 2020-funded project to increase the visibility and raise awareness of European RIs to new communities beyond Europe.

We are looking forward to e-meeting you soon,

Bahne Stechmann, EU-OPENSREEN & RI-VIS
Viridiana Beltran Venegas, BBMRI & RI-VIS
Prof. Trevor Sewell, University of Cape Town

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whova app EXHIBITOR REPORT

EXHIBITOR BOOTH STATS

VISITS	LIKES	COMMENTS
88	0	0

African Laser Centre and the African Lig...

VISITS	LIKES	COMMENTS
104	3	1

BBMRI-ERIC

VISITS	LIKES	COMMENTS
22	0	0

ECRIN-ERIC

VISITS	LIKES	COMMENTS
28	4	0

EMBRC

VISITS	LIKES	COMMENTS
43	5	0

EMPHASIS

VISITS	LIKES	COMMENTS
27	0	0

ENVRI

VISITS	LIKES	COMMENTS
47	2	0

ERINHA

VISITS	LIKES	COMMENTS
11	1	0

ESFRI

VISITS	LIKES	COMMENTS
64	0	2

ESS ERIC

VISITS	LIKES	COMMENTS
49	2	0

EU-OPENSREEN

VISITS	LIKES	COMMENTS
53	0	0

Global Bioluminescence Imaging

VISITS	LIKES	COMMENTS
46	2	0

Instruct

VISITS	LIKES	COMMENTS
16	2	0

International Plant Phenotyping Network ...

VISITS	LIKES	COMMENTS
55	2	0

IS_MIRRI21 project

AFRICA-EUROPE SYMPOSIUM ON RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES

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VISITS LIKES COMMENTS
10 0 0

University of Helsinki, Institute for Atmos...

ADDED VIDEOS TOTAL

8

ADDED LIVE SHOWCASES TOTAL

1

EXHIBITOR PHOTOS UPLOADED

0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0		

USERS CLAIMED RAFFLE

13